

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING MODERN INFORMATION MEDIA IN THE MUSIC EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: In this thesis, opinions are expressed about the important role of pedagogical technologies and pedagogical innovations in the process of music education in the effectiveness of music lessons in modern education.

Key words: pedagogy, technology, innovation, music education, skill, concept.

Introduction:

In the past, music education teachers focused on the basic theory and methods of music education. Today, a modern music teacher should have the skills to use digital resources in his work, be able to work with the latest tools of information technology, be ready for the continuous learning process and join the innovative space of pedagogy, add modern methods should be done. It is necessary to introduce the latest achievements into the educational process, relying on the experience and basic designs of general secondary education, past pedagogy.

Teachers should optimize teaching methods, learn to give voice to students, guide students to active divergent thinking, focus on developing students' interests, actively encourage students to learn music, and they should inspire creativity and intellectual activity.

The need for innovation in modern music education.

Most importantly, in teaching, teachers should use modern teaching tools such as multimedia to deepen students' experience and improve understanding. Also, to stimulate students' interest in music. Second, teachers should allow students to express themselves. Regarding the students' perspective on music, teachers should confirm their own ideas and properly encourage their external views. Teachers should pay attention to this and never stop the various musical aspirations of students. Teachers should objectively assess students' abilities, emphasize the value of learning, and provide positive feedback to students.

With a lack of timely innovations in music learning and education, the classroom becomes lifeless, the classroom environment becomes ineffective, and teaching becomes less effective. Musical education is not fixed, it changes over

time and new knowledge appears. Therefore, teachers should not only keep up with the times, fill in the lack of their knowledge and improve themselves in time, but also optimize the innovative educational environment in time and develop students' divergent thinking. should pay attention.

Teachers should not only adhere to the standard of the curriculum, but should not be limited to them. Teachers should guide students to look outside the classroom and place the knowledge gained from textbooks in the general background of modern society. Such activities are not only a symbol of the value of learning music, but also contribute to the development of students' musical abilities. In a word, innovative musical education is one of the effective ways to develop all-round qualities of students. It plays an important role in the development of students' personality, improvement and development of students' practical, complex skills. Available innovations that can effectively participate in music lessons

1. Multimedia and productivity.

It should be noted that the introduction of innovations and media technologies can provide a concise and interesting presentation of theoretical material. For example, using PowerPoint or Canva, a teacher can create colorful presentations on a lesson topic, and then test the knowledge acquired by students through tests and assignments created through interactive teacher programs (for example, this Learningapps or maybe a test quiz created in Quizzlet resources).

Speaking of learning to sing, virtual resources such as Weibo and WeChat are widely used for musical content in classrooms, providing new opportunities such as the WeSing program. Music teachers can use this program to teach students to sing, and the program can export recorded songs, upload them to Weibo or WeChat for public display, and help students learn music. can increase their interest. Thus, for example, it is possible to organize a song competition among students. This technology not only increases students' interest in vocals, but also reduces the fear of public speaking, which is also very important, although this aspect is often neglected in music education.

Another example is analog piano and other related instrumental music software. Due to the frequent absence of musical instruments in educational institutions, it is impossible to guarantee that every student will have a musical instrument during his studies. An analog instrument music program connected to a smartphone can solve this problem by not only enriching the teaching content, but also by ensuring the quality of the students' education.

Based on objective conditions, applying new technological solutions and innovations to teach music can be very effective in the classroom.

Multimedia software can be a key teaching tool in the classroom. Text, pictures, music and other forms can be added to the learning process to achieve a comprehensive learning effect. Intuitive and easy-to-use toolkit helps to increase students' enthusiasm for learning, encourage them to study musical compositions and theory, and practice musical performance themselves.

It should be noted that the use of new technologies and innovations in the development of musical education in educational institutions places high demands on music teachers, requires teachers to adhere to self-study and improvement, requires keeping up with the times and constantly learning new knowledge and skills regarding modern technologies and innovative teaching methods.

Innovation in music education primarily changes the relationship between teachers and students. In the past, when new technologies were not yet widely used, the concept of music education focused on musical skills and more emphasis on improving performance techniques. However, music education can change significantly in terms of innovation.

2. Innovative pedagogical technologies.

In a traditional music classroom, the teacher plays an important role. In a one-hour lesson, the teacher is completely self-taught, and the students passively absorb the material that they offer, which leads to a decrease in student interest in learning and a decrease in learning efficiency.

Today, there are many pedagogical technologies that encourage students to learn music and arouse their interest in the educational process. Such technologies include problem-based learning technology:

- design technology;
- technology of educational and methodical game activity;
- interactive technologies.

We will touch on some of them for illustration.

The project method can be effectively implemented in music education. The educational project is considered as a means of activating cognitive activity, developing creativity (creative thinking), research skills, communication skills in a team, and forming certain personal qualities. The content of the projects guides students to understand the eternal themes of art and life in their individual and collective activities.

Educational and gaming technology can be effectively incorporated into music lessons in primary education. For example, in the process of learning musical instruments, children can choose different instruments from the ones offered by the teacher. Then it is fashionable to sit the children in a circle on the floor, and children with the same tools sit together when the picture is shown (or in different places at the discretion of the teacher). The teacher can show several pictures (or pictures on the electronic board) at the same time to help the children create a certain musical sound. This technique-based lesson helps children explore the different sounds of musical instruments, and learn to work together to create beautiful music.

In the process of implementing the innovations proposed above, first of all, students can become more active by involving them in the learning process and make them independent participants of the learning process. Secondly, the introduction of innovative methods will pay more attention to the interaction and communication between teachers and students, as well as students of the class. In such conditions, the classroom ceases to be a boring classroom and becomes an area for spending fun and productive time.

In traditional music teaching in educational institutions, students do not have a sense of belonging to the learning process due to a single teaching method, which cannot stimulate students' interest in learning music and this in turn leads to the gradual decline of music education into the formal course. With the advent of technology, as well as innovative ways of teaching music, students are provided with more resources and learning opportunities.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, I would like to emphasize that music has the function of expressing emotions and educating students' aesthetic views. With the beginning of the era of modern technologies and innovations, educational institutions should fully understand the effectiveness of introducing new media technologies in education, deepen the reform of music education, and integrate new media technologies and pedagogical innovations with music education in educational institutions. and learn to effectively integrate, achieve and encourage good interactions with students.

In today's society, through new media technologies and general innovations in music education, it is possible not only to increase students' enthusiasm for learning music, but also to modernize the outdated and familiar education system.

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